

Building Social Engagement: The Role of Personal Traits and FOMO in the Sustained Use of Social Commerce Platforms

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to examine the influence of personal traits and Fear of Missing Out (FOMO) on the continued use of social commerce platforms and its consequences for social engagement. Utilizing a quantitative approach, data were collected through a structured questionnaire distributed to 90 respondents who have previously engaged in online shopping via social commerce. The analysis employed Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to assess the relationships between variables. The findings reveal that personal traits significantly and positively affect the continued use of social commerce platforms, while FOMO also plays a crucial role in driving user engagement. Moreover, the study concludes that sustained use of these platforms enhances social engagement, indicating that users not only seek transactional benefits but also social interactions. The research highlights the need for social commerce platforms to consider psychological factors when designing user experiences to foster long-term engagement.

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KEYWORDS:

Fear of Missing Out, Personal Traits, Social Commerce, Social Engagement

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the use of Social Networking Sites (SNS) has grown rapidly along with the affordability of internet technology and electronic devices. SNS, better known as social media, are in high demand by various groups because they are able to provide information and entertainment in one application platform. Users can spend hours on social media if the content displayed is interesting and varied. Apart from being a means of communication, SNS is now also utilised as a social commerce platform that enables online transactions while increasing social engagement.

Social engagement refers to interactions that take place within online communities, whether through individual social media such as Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, and LinkedIn, or on blogs, forums, and review sites. Through these interactions, consumers can share their experiences with specific brands, increase product recommendations, and expand marketing reach.

According to the We Are Social report (2022), internet users spend 60 to 180 minutes per day on social media, with younger users and women spending longer. In addition, social media has evolved from a mere source of information to a commerce platform (Hossain & Kim, 2020). While e-commerce platforms are still the primary choice for selling, many sellers are using social media as an alternative means to capture potential customers through informative education and influencers.

During the pandemic, social commerce has increased rapidly and helped MSMEs increase their sales (kumparan.com, 2021). The most frequently used social media by Indonesians, followed by Facebook, Instagram, and TikTok, which have seen significant increases. Social commerce incorporates social elements such as attention, sharing, communication, discussion, and interaction in e-commerce transactions.

From a consumer perspective, social commerce includes store selection, product comparison, interaction with influencers, and evaluation and sharing of experiences after purchase. Meanwhile, from the perspective of e-commerce companies, social commerce enables marketing, promotion and sales of products through web 2.0 applications and cooperation with influencers. The two main features of social commerce are shopping guidance and interaction and sharing between users and companies.

Academic research on social commerce continues to grow. Zheng et al [1] developed a semi-supervised system to estimate the quality of online reviews and found that social features contribute greatly to the system. Hajli [2] stated that interaction in social commerce increases trust and purchase intention, while [3] examined consumer decision-making mechanisms in social commerce.

The initial survey showed that consumers first use social commerce platforms because they are influenced by online promotions and product displays. However, a first experience that does not meet expectations can lead to hesitation in continued use. Barger et al [4] found that customers no longer trust advertisements from online stores, so other variables such as influencers, adequate information, ease of use, satisfaction, benefits, data security, service, and personal characteristics of users become important factors

in determining reuse intentions.

Li et al.[5] state that influencers, adequate information, and personal traits of users are the main triggers for using social commerce. Chen & Chang,[3] revealed that influencers' charm and professionalism have a positive effect on users' recommendation intention to use social commerce platforms, especially TikTok Live. Safitri et al.[6] also found that influencers have a significant influence on the intention to use social media platforms. Social technology, social experience, and personal traits influence the intention to use social commerce. However, Alabdullatif & Velázquez-Iturbide [7]) found that personal traits do not have a significant effect on the continued use of online course platforms.

Previous research shows mixed results regarding the influence of personal traits on the use of social commerce platforms. Some studies associate personal traits with Fear of Missing Out (FOMO), which is social anxiety due to fear of being left behind [8], [9]. Przybylski et al.[9] found that individuals with high FOMO used social media more frequently and were more prone to using mobile phones while driving. According to self-determination theory [10] FOMO arises when basic psychological needs such as competence, autonomy, and relatedness are not met, which encourages individuals to be more active in social media.

Several other studies have also highlighted the influence of personal traits on perceived ease of use in the context of technology. Nov & Ye,[11] found that openness affects a person's innovativeness in information systems. Özbek et al.[12]found that extraversion affects perceived ease of use. Özbek et al.[12]also stated that personal traits have a positive influence on perceived ease of use in the acceptance of smartphone technology. Friendly individuals tend to find technology more useful, while individuals with high neuroticism tend to find technology less useful. In addition, individuals with a high level of openness are more receptive to new technology.

FOMO has been shown to increase social media use, especially among young people [9], [13], [14]. Alt [13]found that individuals with high extrinsic motivation tend to have higher levels of FOMO and use social media more frequently. Billieux [15]showed that socially anxious individuals use social media to seek social reassurance. A study in India [14] showed that FOMO is associated with higher social media use. In addition, FOMO was found to be a major predictor of smartphone usage.

Perceived ease of use F. D. Davis [16]is the level of user comfort in adopting new technology. Customers tend to accept technology if they find it easy to use. Ease of use in business transactions is an important factor in increasing technology adoption [17], [18]. Other studies confirm that perceived benefits are influenced by perceived ease of use in the technology acceptance model (TAM) [16], [19]. According to [19], consumers will be more likely to adopt technologies that are considered easy to use in their shopping activities. Therefore, social commerce vendors need to improve perceived ease of use among potential customers.

II. METHOD

This research was conducted using quantitative methods with a causality approach. An explanatory survey design was also carried out to explain the relationship between the variables studied. The population and sample in this study are consumers who have made online purchases on social commerce platforms. Samples using non-probability sampling with a sample size between 90 and 180. The data collection technique was carried out by distributing questionnaires containing questions about the factors in using the social commerce platform using Google Form. Data analysis was carried out using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method to test the relationship between variables.

III. RESULTS

Respondent Characteristics

This study involved 90 respondents who had previously made online purchases through social commerce platforms. Demographic data was collected to provide insights into the social and economic background of the respondents, as well as other relevant factors that may influence the results of the study. Among the participants, 73.3% (66 people) were female, while 26.7% (24 people) were male, indicating a predominant female presence in the study, which is in line with the trend of higher engagement in social commerce among women. In terms of age, the majority (45.6% or 41 respondents) were within the range of 25 to 32 years, followed by 23.3% (21 respondents) aged 33 to 40 years, 15.6% (14 respondents) aged 41 to 47 years, 10% (9 respondents) aged 17 to 24 years, and 5.6% (5 respondents) aged above 47 years. Most respondents (90%) were employed, including private employees, civil servants and self-employed, while the remaining 10% were students or recent graduates, reflecting a minimum education level of high school to college. In terms of monthly income, 70% of respondents earn above IDR3,000,000, while 22.2% earn between IDR1,000,000 and IDR3,000,000, and 7.8% earn below IDR1,000,000, often relying on parental support. In addition, 60% of respondents actively use social commerce platforms daily or almost daily, 25% use them several times a week, and 15% use them less than once a week. The most frequently used platforms are Instagram, TikTok, Facebook, and YouTube.

In this study, validity and reliability tests were conducted to ensure that the data collection instruments met good research quality standards. The validity test aims to measure whether each question item is able to measure the intended variable precisely and accurately. Meanwhile, the reliability test aims to test the consistency of the instrument measurement results when repeated under the same conditions.

Validity Test

Validity was tested using the item-total correlation method through Pearson Product Moment analysis. The validity test results show that all statement items on personal traits, Fear of Missing Out (FoMO), perceived ease of use, continued use of social commerce platforms and social engagement have a significant correlation value with the total instrument score, with a correlation coefficient of 0.634 to 0.934 where these results are above 0.30 at the 0.05 significance level. This indicates that all items are valid and can be used to measure variable constructs appropriately.

Reliability Test

Instrument reliability was tested using the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. Based on the test results, the Cronbach's Alpha value for each variable is as follows: personal traits variable obtained a value of 0.830, Fear of Missing Out variable 0.837, continued use of social commerce platform variable 0.891 and social engagement variable 0.896. This value is above the 0.70 threshold recommended in the social research literature, so it can be concluded that this research instrument is reliable and produces consistent measurements.

Inferential Analysis Results

1) Outer Model

In the measurement model, the relationship between indicators and constructs is evaluated by assessing validity and reliability. Evaluation of the measurement model (outer model) aims to determine the validity and reliability of the indicators used to measure the research variables. Research variables include personal traits, Fear of Missing Out (FoMO), perceived ease of use, continued use of social commerce platforms and social engagement measured by reflexive indicators. Construct validity was analysed by testing convergent validity and discriminant validity while reliability was assessed by composite reliability.

(1) Convergent validity test

Variable	Indicator	Factor Loading
Personal Traits (X_1)	5	0,740- 0,902
FOMO (X_2)	4	0,812 - 0,904
Perceived Ease of Used (X_3)	3	0,913 - 0,953
Continued Use of Social Commerce Platform (Y_1)	3	0,817 - 0,910
Social engagement (Y_2)	3	0,877 - 0,957

The results of convergent validity testing show that all variable indicator outer loading values have values above 0.50. Thus, it can be concluded that the indicators have met the convergent validity requirements.

(2) Discriminant validity using factor loading and Average Variance Extracted tests

Another method that can be used is to compare the square root of the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) for each variable with the correlation value between other variables in the model. If the square root value of the AVE of each construct is greater than the correlation value between the construct and other constructs in the model, it is said to have good discriminant validity value (Hair et al., 2017).

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Personal Traits (X_1)	0,696
FOMO (X_2)	0,879
Perceived Ease of Used (X_3)	0,809
Continued Use of Social Commerce Platform (Y_1)	0,807
Social engagement (Y_2)	0,837

The data shows that the AVE value of each variable has an AVE value greater than 0.50. Thus the model can be said to be valid.

(3). Composite reliability

A measuring instrument is said to be reliable if the composite reliability value is > 0.70 (Hair et al., 2017).

Variable	Composite Reliability	Cronbachs Alpha	Remarks
Personal Traits (X_1)	0,851	0,963	Reliabel
FOMO (X_2)	0,843	0,817	Reliabel
Perceived Ease of Used (X_3)	0,946	0,940	Reliabel
Continued Use of Social Commerce Platform (Y_1)	0,912	0,908	Reliabel
Social Engagement (Y_2)	0,932	0,930	Reliabel

Based on the data above, it can be explained that the AVE value of each variable has a composite reliability value and Cronbachs alpha greater than 0.70, thus, it can be explained that the variable has good reliability.

2) Inner model

(1) R-Square Test

Testing the structural model or inner model with PLS is done by looking at the R-Square (R²) value which is a goodness-fit model test. The R-Square value for each endogenous latent variable is the predictive power of the structural model. Changes in the R-Square value can be used to explain the effect of certain exogenous latent variables on endogenous latent variables. An R-Square value above 0.75 explains that the model is strong, 0.50-0.75 is moderate, and 0.25- 0.50 is weak.

Variable	R-Square
Continued Use of Social Commerce Platform (Y ₁)	0,735
Social engagement (Y ₂)	0,759

Data that the R-Square value for continued use of social commerce platform (Y₁) reaches 0.735. This means that 73.5 per cent of the variation in the variable continued use of social commerce platform (Y₁) is explained by the variables of personal traits, Fear of Missing Out (FoMO), perceived ease of use. Similarly, the variation of social engagement (Y₂) is 0.759, indicating that 75.9 per cent of the variation is explained by the continued use of social commerce platform variable.

Overall, these results indicate that the PLS model used has good predictive relevance, with most of the R-Square values being above 0.70 which is an indication that the independent variables in the model are able to explain most of the variation in the dependent variable.

3) Hypothesis Testing

Path Coefficient

No	Variable	Coefficient Correlation	t Statistics	p Values	Remarks
H ₁	Personal Traits (X ₁) ->Continued Use of Social Commerce Platform (Y ₁)	0,902	73,071	0,000	Significant
H ₂	FOMO (X ₂) -> Continued Use of Social Commerce Platform (Y ₁)	0,118	2,066	0,039	Significant
H ₃	Perceived Ease of Used (X ₁) -> Continued Use of Social Commerce Platform (Y ₁)	0,911	67,169	0,000	Significant
H ₄	Continued Use of Social Commerce Platform (Y ₁) -> Social engagement (Y ₂)	0,778	21,880	0,000	Significant

Path coefficient results that explain the various relationships between variables that influence the intention to use digital bank services. Based on the results of the data processing presented in the 4 hypothesis formulations proposed, there are 4 (four) hypotheses that get support because they produce a p-value <0.05 or produce a t-statistic value > 1.96, namely hypotheses H₁, H₂, H₃, and H₄.

IV. DISCUSSION

(1) The influence of personal traits on continued use of social commerce platforms

The test results show that personal traits have a positive and significant effect on the continued use of social commerce platforms. The results of this test prove that hypothesis 1 (H₁) proposed in this study which states that personal traits have a positive and significant effect on continued use of social commerce platforms can be accepted.

Research that reveals that personal traits have a positive and significant effect on the continued use of social commerce platforms highlights how the unique psychological characteristics of individuals are the foundation of the formation of their digital shopping habits. The positive effect indicates that the stronger a particular personality trait is in a person, the higher their intention and frequency to continue using the platform. Meanwhile, significance proves that this relationship is no coincidence, but a strong and consistent pattern that can be statistically verified, extending beyond the research sample to a wider population of users. Some of the key traits that are often shown to have a direct impact include extroverted personality types who use the platform as a means to gain social validation and interact, so they return to share their shopping experiences or see responses from their social networks. Furthermore, people with high levels of openness to experience tend to be loyal users as they enjoy the process of exploring new features, innovative products and the latest trends that the platform constantly presents. On the other hand, conscientiousness can motivate continued use of social commerce platforms through a planning mechanism; users with this trait routinely utilise the

platform to compare prices, read in-depth reviews and manage wish lists, making the platform part of their structured shopping decision-making ritual. Even neuroticism may contribute, where individuals seek release or distraction from daily stress by browsing and impulse shopping. Thus, these findings confirm that user loyalty to a social commerce platform is not a homogeneous phenomenon, but rather highly personalised based on each individual's psychological map, where successful platforms are ultimately those that are able to embrace and cater to the diverse needs of these different personality types. Chen & Chang [3] stated that personal traits positively influence a person's desire to continue using online application.

(2) The influence of FoMO on continued use of social commerce platforms

The test results show that FOMO has a positive and significant effect on continued use of social commerce platforms. The results of this test prove that hypothesis 2 (H2) proposed in this study which states that FOMO has a positive and significant effect on continued use of social commerce platforms can be accepted.

The finding that FOMO (Fear Of Missing Out) has a positive and significant effect on continued use of social commerce platforms reveals crucial psychological and behavioural dynamics in the modern digital shopping world. FOMO, which is the social anxiety of missing out on favourable information, experiences or opportunities enjoyed by others, turns out to serve as a very powerful motivational driver. In the context of platforms such as TikTok Shop, Instagram Shopping or Shopee Live, this feeling is consistently triggered by specially designed elements, such as flash sales with countdown timers, notifications stating stock is running low, or livestreams featuring crowds of enthusiastic shoppers. The positive influence here means that the more intense the feeling of FOMO that a user experiences, the more frequent and engaged they will be in using the platform. They will return again and again, not just out of necessity, but to ease anxiety by feeling connected and not missing out. Meanwhile, the word significant confirms that this relationship is not a mere coincidence, but has been statistically proven to be robust through research, suggesting that this pattern is a real phenomenon and can reliably predict user behaviour. Ultimately, FOMO facilitates the formation of a habitual cycle of visual triggers on the platform generating anxiety, which is then alleviated by the act of opening the app, browsing the product, and finally making a purchase. It is this repetitive cycle that crystallises continued use behaviour, making the user not just a one-time consumer, but an active part of the platform ecosystem that returns regularly, thus ensuring the long-term survival and growth of social commerce businesses.

In the context of social media marketing and influencer marketing, FoMO is widely used in marketing. Thus, advertising content on social media that appeals to anxiety relief leads to higher intensity of social media use. Joo et al. [19] investigated whether adding FOMO messages to Facebook adverts increases continued use of the social commerce platform. The results found that consumers performed better in ad recall and recognition when FOMO content was present. Hamutoglu [20] found that FoMO has a significant impact on the continued use of social commerce platforms and is also highly correlated with collectivism, ethnic identity and culture. The presence of FoMO will ultimately result in a higher probability of purchase behaviour. For example Li [5] studied the direct and indirect effects of FoMO appeals on purchase likelihood, and suggested that FoMO-laden appeals may influence consumers' purchase intentions on an ongoing basis.

(3) The Influence of perceived ease of use terhadap continued use of social commerce platform

The test results show that perceived ease of use has a positive and significant effect on continued use of social commerce platforms. The results of this test prove that hypothesis 3 (H3) proposed in this study which states that perceived ease of use has a positive and significant effect on continued use of social commerce platforms can be accepted.

Research that reveals that perceived ease of use has a positive and significant effect on continued use of social commerce platforms confirms the fundamental principle in technology adoption that users will consistently return to platforms that are perceived to be easy and uncomplicated. The positive effect means that the higher the users' belief that the platform is easy to navigate, learn and operate to achieve their goals (such as searching for products or completing purchases), the stronger their intention and habit of using it repeatedly. Meanwhile, significance confirms that this relationship is not a coincidence, but a strong and reliable predictor that has been statistically tested, suggesting that ease of use is a critical prerequisite for retaining users in the long term. This concept is rooted in the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) proposed by [16] where perceived ease of use is one of the core beliefs that shape users' attitudes towards a system.

Recent studies in the context of continued use of social commerce platforms prove its validity. A study by [2] found that ease of use of social commerce platforms not only drives intention to adopt, but also increases perceived usefulness and ultimately builds intention to continue participating. In practice, this translates into a seamless user experience: intuitive interfaces such as on Instagram Shopping or TikTok Shop enable a seamless transition from viewing content to transacting, simple payment processes, and intelligent search and recommendation features. When users face no friction or significant technical obstacles, the level of effort required to shop is low. This reduces psychological barriers, increases satisfaction, and builds positive associations with the platform. Ultimately, perceived ease of use creates the foundation of a stress-free experience, which motivates users to make the platform their primary destination, thus ensuring continued usage as a natural consequence of user-centred design.

(4) The consequences of continued use of social commerce platforms on social engagement

The test results show that the consequences of continued use of social commerce platforms on social engagement are positive and significant. These test results prove that hypothesis 4 (H4) proposed in this study can be accepted.

The finding that the consequence of continued use of social commerce platforms on social engagement is positive and significant reveals that the active and repeated habit of using the platform is not just a transactional activity, but instead serves as a catalyst to strengthen and expand users' social interactions. The positive effect indicates that the more intensely and consistently a person uses the social commerce platform, the quantity and quality of their social engagement such as sharing experiences, providing comments, asking for opinions, and building a sense of community will also increase. The significance value confirms that this relationship is not an illusion or coincidence, but a strong and statistically verified cause-and-effect relationship, which illustrates a consistent trend among users.

Research by [5] on social commerce has proven that the use of such platforms is not only for shopping, but also to fulfil social needs by facilitating the exchange of information and support among users, which in turn increases social engagement. Furthermore, a study by [2] found that participation in social commerce platforms creates a social support environment, where loyal users are actively involved in the community by providing reviews, recommendations, and likes, all of which are tangible forms of social engagement. This mechanism works because social commerce platforms are essentially hybrid ecosystems that bring together commercial and social networking elements. When a user continuously views a friend's posts, participates in an interactive live stream, or engages in a product discussion, they are indirectly nurturing and deepening their social relationships. These repeated interactions build social capital, mutual trust, and community ties. Thus, continued use of social commerce platforms transforms the platform from a mere digital marketplace to a dynamic social space, where each visit not only has the potential to generate transactions, but also enriches the fabric of users' social interactions, proving that commercial and social value can grow simultaneously.

V. CONCLUSION

The findings from this research are a complex phenomenon driven by the dynamic interaction between technological, psychological, and social factors. The research findings consistently prove that perceived ease of use, psychological drives such as FOMO, and personal traits not only positively and significantly influence the formation of usage habits, but also ultimately result in positive social consequences, namely increased social engagement. This causal relationship confirms that successful social commerce platforms operate as an integrated hybrid ecosystem, where commercial value and social value are mutually reinforcing. Users not only come to transact, but also to fulfil their psychological and social needs, which then binds them to keep coming back to the platform, creating a continuous cycle of usage.

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VII. DISCLOSURE

The author reports no conflicts of interest in this work. [Each manuscript needs to include a disclosure of financial interest or other. The author declares that there are no financial, commercial, or personal relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest in the conduct and publication of this research. The author reports no conflicts of interest and received no financial support for the research, authorship, or publication of this article.

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